

Addressing the Elephant in the Room: Processions in Mughal India

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Abstract

As the advent of gunpowder and marksmanship gradually phased out the elephant from the battlefields, the Indian elephant firmly remained as an integral part of royal processions throughout the subcontinent, all the way up to the early twentieth century. On the heels of these military advancements, the Mughals from Central Asia arrived in north India in 1526. However, despite their equestrian Timurid background, the Mughals found themselves compelled to adapt to the deeply entrenched elephant-centered practices of their newly conquered domain. At the outset, this paper seeks to explore how the Mughals employed the elephant in imperial processions as a strategic tool for statecraft and propaganda, one that aimed to project imperial authority while simultaneously affirming the emperor's sovereignty and legitimacy. By attempting to offer a coherent narrative on processions in Mughal India and the role of the elephant within it, this paper will examine the symbolic significance of the elephant in the case of two broad types of royal processions - the imperial march and the Friday prayer procession, both of which placed the emperor, seated atop his caparisoned elephant, as the central focus of the procession. Through this, the study aims to shed more light on the close relationship between the elephant and kingship in India.

Keywords: *Mughal Empire, processions, elephant, kingship, Indian history*

1. Introduction

Despite the centuries of precedent of having the elephant serve as a key symbol of Indian kingship both on and off the battlefield, the sixteenth century saw an unforeseen development challenge this historical equilibrium. With the advancements and proliferation of guns and artillery, riding an elephant into battle became an easy target for skilled marksmen. Nevertheless, this new reality and the subsequent diminishing role of the elephant at the battlefield did not seem to affect its relationship with the ideas of kingship in India in the same manner.²⁷⁶ On the contrary, it was expertly adapted to fit the changing needs of representing Indian kingship, something overtly observable during the heyday of Mughal empire (1526-1707) in India, which continued well past the end of the dynasty in 1857.²⁷⁷

Arriving in India in 1526 with a background of Timurid equestrian culture from Central Asia, the Mughals found themselves in a position where they were compelled to acclimatise and subsequently adapt to the elephant-based kingship traditions that existed in the subcontinent.²⁷⁸ By the late sixteenth century, the elephant had become a state propaganda tool to not only extend and sustain imperial Mughal identity but also to represent the emperor's sovereignty and legitimacy. Through studying this changing role of the elephant in the Mughal case, particularly regarding its central role in imperial processions, this paper aims to examine an underexplored area of elephant-kingship ties in Mughal India. For this, the paper will succinctly examine the meanings attached to the elephant in broadly two types of Mughal processions where the elephant represented the Mughal Emperor - the imperial march and the Friday processions. Focusing on the elephant in these processions further allows for addressing its remarkable relationship with kingship in India.

²⁷⁶ The elephant would continue to be used for transportation and logistics. Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities in North India, 1200–1600 CE," *The Indian Economic & Social History Review* 57, no. 2 (2020): 139–69, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019464620912614>, 154, 159.

²⁷⁷ Although Babur established his kingdom in 1526 in north India, Humayun, his successor, lost his kingdom briefly to Sher Shah Suri and had to seek Safavid aid. Humayun's recapture of the kingdom in 1555 followed by his untimely death in 1556 set the stage for Akbar to lead this fledgling kingdom into an empire. For detailed history of the Mughal Empire and its beginnings, please check: John F Richards, *The Mughal Empire* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995); Richard M. Eaton, *India in the Persianate Age: 1000-1765* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2019).

²⁷⁸ Jane Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power*: Elephants and Gendered Authority in the Mughal World," in *Conflict, Negotiation, and Coexistence: Rethinking Human–Elephant Relations in South Asia*, ed. Piers Locke and Jane Buckingham (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2016), 92–114.

2. *Elephas Maximus Indicus*

It was not uncommon for an incoming army into north India to have to face the ruling monarch's elephantry in battle, often to their shock. This encounter has been repeatedly recorded over the centuries. Some of the prominent instances of this encounter with the Indian elephant (*Elephas Maximus Indicus*) includes Alexander the Great, the king of Macedon who began his Indian campaign in 327 BCE after his conquest of the Achaemenid Persian Empire; Mahmud of Ghazni's military expeditions into India from today's Afghanistan starting in 1001 CE; Timur, the Turco-Mongol commander from Central Asia, who captured Delhi in 1398; Babur, who came from Ferghana (Uzbekistan) to establish Mughal rule in north India in 1526, among many others.²⁷⁹ Among them, the cases that subsequently led to establishment of a state tended to also lead to a situation where many extant traditions, such as the elephant, became tools that had to be adopted and adapted to fit the changing needs of the ruling elite.

Some of the earliest known mentions of the Indian elephant in the Indian subcontinent can be found among the seals of the Indus Valley Civilization (3300 – 1300 BCE) which contain intricately carved figures of elephants, hinting at the visibility that elephants occupied in that society in order to be chosen to be depicted on their seals.²⁸⁰ Over the centuries, elephants came to be actively employed in warfare in India to the extent that by the time Alexander the Great arrived in India in 327 BCE, it is recorded that elephants instilled awe upon his troops.²⁸¹ Although Alexander won the battle, the reputation of elephants were set such that one of his successors, Seleucus Nicator, founder of the Seleucid dynasty, is reported to have ceded four provinces in 305 BCE in exchange for five hundred elephants from the Indian ruler, Chandragupta Maurya.²⁸² In that era, it is worth noting that the ruler often mounted the biggest elephant under his command and they were exclusively trained for the personal use of the ruler,

²⁷⁹ Thomas R. Trautmann, "Alexander and the Elephants," *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, April 10, 2025, 1–24, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0010417525000027>; S Jabir Raza, "Indian Elephant Corps Under The Ghaznavids," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 73 (2012): 212–22, 213–214; Justin Marozzi, *Tamerlane: Sword of Islam, Conqueror of the World* (Cambridge: Da Capo Press, 2006), 238, 242, 265–269.

²⁸⁰ B P Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 18 (1955): 51–57, 51.

²⁸¹ Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 52.

²⁸² Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 54.

with estimates claiming 9000 elephants in the stables of Chandragupta Maurya.²⁸³ However, the Indian elephant helped chart the course of history not just in the Indian subcontinent, but in places very far away from it as well. An example of this is Timur's use of war elephants in the Battle of Ankara (Türkiye) in 1402 where elephants were significant in ensuring Timur's victory over the Ottomans.²⁸⁴ It is highly possible that these war elephants were part of the war booty that Timur had captured in his sack of Delhi in 1398, which he subsequently took to his capital of Samarkand.²⁸⁵

This revered status of the elephant in warfare however did not last. In addition to its slow pace, the possibility of elephants to rout in the midst of battle, combined with the overall advancement in military technology and marksmanship by the sixteenth century caused elephants to become prime targets in the battlefield, leading them to be channelled more towards other non-military purposes, particularly in ceremonial settings.²⁸⁶ We can notice this overall shift in the following examples. During Timur's conquest of India in 1398, battle preparations were directed mostly at tackling the threat of the elephant to make them rout as early as possible.²⁸⁷ Trenches were dug strategically at estimated points of an elephant charge and camels loaded with inflammable materials were set on fire and unleashed towards the elephants in order to create havoc, aiming to make the elephants go berserk.²⁸⁸ However, by the time of Babur's conquest in 1526, due to significant advancement in gunpowder based weaponry and skilled marksmanship, the elephant was hardly the threat it was during Timur's time and instead became prime targets for the marksmen.²⁸⁹ This was evident in how despite being at a numerical disadvantage, Babur was able to defeat Ibrahim Lodi's significantly larger but technologically inferior army, which was estimated to have had hundreds of war elephants.²⁹⁰ Although cavalry formed the core of Mughal armies during Babur's campaigns, the elephant was soon incorporated into both the army as well as into Mughal culture itself. However, it is the role of

²⁸³ Paul J Kosmin, *The Land of the Elephant Kings: Space, Territory, and Ideology in the Seleucid Empire* (Harvard University Press, 2014), 34.

²⁸⁴ Dimitris J. Kastritsis, "Introduction: The Battle of Ankara and Its Consequences," in *The Sons of Bayezid: Empire Building and Representation in the Ottoman Civil War of 1402-1413* (Leiden: Brill, 2007), 1-40.

²⁸⁵ Bamber Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls* (London: Constable, 1998), 12-13.

²⁸⁶ Andrew De la Garza, *The Mughal Empire at War: Babur, Akbar and the Indian Military Revolution, 1500-1605* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2016), 6; Sinha, "Elephants in Ancient Indian Army," 51, 56.

²⁸⁷ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 12.

²⁸⁸ Marozzi, *Tamerlane*, 268-269.

²⁸⁹ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 33.

²⁹⁰ Andrew De la Garza, *The Mughal Empire at War*, 41-42.

the elephant in this cultural spectrum, particularly in its representation of the Mughal Emperor in processions, that will be the focus of this article.

3. The Elephant under Mughal Kingship

Babur's Indian campaign was not an unusual occurrence for its time, especially considering that he was a direct descendent of Timur. But unlike Timur, who did not stay in India for long, the turbulent political atmosphere of Central Asia during Babur's time significantly contributed towards his decision to establish a kingdom in north India in 1526.²⁹¹ While this commenced Mughal dominion in north India, the plethora of religions, ethnicities, languages and cultures that this unique situation brought together necessitated the overall need for a stable rule brought about through adopting a syncretic approach towards ruling, one that was inherently eclectic in nature, paving the way for a composite Mughal culture and society.²⁹² This outlook contributed immensely towards the meteoric rise that the Mughals would see in the following decades, which also allowed room for bringing in the elephant as a tool to serve the needs of this newly emergent state.

Before the Mughals, the rulers of the Delhi Sultanate (1206-1526) had faced a similar predicament, which they had resolved by absorbing the existing Indian notion associated with the elephant to represent authority.²⁹³ In fact, scholars posit that the Delhi Sultanate's endurance depended somewhat on their control over the supply of elephants and horses while depriving it to their rivals.²⁹⁴ This was partly because the image of a monarch riding an elephant was viewed not only as the symbol of sovereignty but also with the understanding where the elephant itself came to represent the sovereign in large parts of India.²⁹⁵ Instead of merely repeating the same approach, the Mughals eclectically utilised this existing state of affairs to their advantage by

²⁹¹ Stephen F Dale, *The Garden of the Eight Paradises: Babur and the Culture of Empire in Central Asia, Afghanistan and India (1483-1530)* (Leiden: Brill, 2004), 292.

²⁹² Catherine B Asher and Cynthia Talbot, *India before Europe* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 115.

²⁹³ Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities in North India, 1200–1600CE," *The Indian Economic & Social History Review* 57, no. 2 (2020): 139–69, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019464620912614>, 147; Simon Digby, *War-Horse and Elephant in the Delhi Sultanate: A Study of Military Supplies* (Oxford: Orient Monographs, 1971), 20.

²⁹⁴ Ali Anooshahr, "The Elephant and the Sovereign: India circa 1000 CE," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 28, no. 4 (October 2018): 615–44, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1356186318000093>, 618-619.

²⁹⁵ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 147.

adding new symbolic meanings to the image of the imperial elephant, overtly visible in their processions. However, before delving into that, it is essential to explore the relationship between the elephant and the Mughal Emperor in more detail, particularly as it evolved during the reign of Babur's grandson, Akbar.

Akbar, the third emperor of the Mughal dynasty who ruled from 1556-1605, succeeded his father Humayun at the young age of fourteen.²⁹⁶ During his nearly fifty-year reign, Akbar greatly expanded and consolidated the empire which his father had retaken only in 1555 from the Sur dynasty.²⁹⁷ In tandem with this overall expansion of territory, by the 1580s, Akbar's domains ensured him as the sole ruler with the largest number of elephants and the one with the most advanced and largest arsenal of gunpowder based weaponry in the subcontinent.²⁹⁸ This meant that he could break away from the Sultanate system of rule where the empire was ruled through tributary kings and instead rule directly as the emperor.²⁹⁹

The consolidation of Mughal realms under Akbar also made the elephant the most visible symbol of imperial sovereignty in the subcontinent once again. The magnitude of this close ruler-elephant association can be seen from the state control over elephantry. For instance, historians estimate that the total captive population of elephants in the empire was 17,000 in 1595, where the Mughal imperial stables alone are estimated to have held around 5,000 elephants.³⁰⁰ Here, the elephant served many roles when it represented the empire. Outside of imperial processions, the elephant was the imperial mount of the emperor on his hunting expeditions as well. Elephants were employed to hunt other elephants too, but unlike other animals, the elephants caught in a hunt were seldom killed and were most often captured and trained to be used for the empire.³⁰¹ Akbar himself participated in hunting and capturing elephants and the biggest and strongest male elephants captured from the hunts were trained and adopted into the imperial service as *khasa* (special) elephants (Fig. 1).³⁰² Once taken into the imperial stables, the elephants were classified into seven categories where the food, the type of

²⁹⁶ Abraham Eraly, *The Mughal Throne: The Saga of India's Great Emperors* (Phoenix, 2004), 115-116.

²⁹⁷ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 337.

²⁹⁸ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 160.

²⁹⁹ Smith, *The Oxford History of India*, 160.

³⁰⁰ Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others in the Mughal Landscape," in *Shifting Ground: People, Animals, and Mobility in India's Environmental History*, ed. Mahesh Rangarajan and K Sivaramkrishnan (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2014), 88-108, 99.

³⁰¹ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 149.

³⁰² Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 100.

care and servants that were assigned to these elephants were based on their respective category.³⁰³ In addition to starting a specialised breeding program for these elephants which was previously not practised in the subcontinent, Akbar also personally inspected his elephants and the *khasa* elephants were reserved to be used only by him.³⁰⁴

Royal entertainment was another major role that was fulfilled by imperial elephants. Elephant races and elephant fights (Fig. 2) were common forms of entertainment, which were reserved only for the emperor.³⁰⁵ Akbar was known to have immensely enjoyed watching elephant fights throughout his youth and is famously known to have fought in many elephant duels himself, often at considerable risk to his own life.³⁰⁶ This legendary reputation since his youth for taming and bringing rogue or drunk elephants under control was tactfully incorporated into the narrative that the emperor was able to avoid all the dangers due to his divinity and closeness to God and was portrayed as a warning to any opposition to his rule that the emperor feared nothing.³⁰⁷ This development was coupled with the fact that Akbar by this time was hailed as an emanation of the Light of God and as a superior semi-divine being specially chosen by God to rule.³⁰⁸ His lineage was traced back not only to Timur and Genghis Khan, but also to many divine religious figures and ultimately back to the Sun itself, which was applied as solar symbolisms in various avenues of Mughal art and architecture during not only Akbar's reign but also during those of his immediate successors.³⁰⁹ Through the combination of these varied factors, the image of the emperor grew more divine and less human while his famous feats in subduing unruly elephants was expertly utilised to add on to this divine narrative. This would also be interpreted as Akbar bringing the symbol of Indian kingship under his control whereby he was the undisputed ruler who could tame and bring to submission any rebellious elephant or, symbolically, any rebellious Indian ruler.³¹⁰

³⁰³ Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 101.

³⁰⁴ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 9; Divyabhanusinh, "Lions, Cheetahs, and Others," 101.

³⁰⁵ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁶ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁷ Anooshahr, "The Elephant and Imperial Continuities," 161.

³⁰⁸ Catherine B Asher, "A Ray from the Sun: Mughal Ideology and the Visual Construction of the Divine," in *The Presence of Light: Divine Radiance and Religious Experience*, ed. Matthew Kapstein (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2004), 161–94, 170; Anna Malecka, "Solar Symbolism of the Mughal Thrones. A Preliminary Note," *Arts Asiatiques* 54, no. 1 (1999): 24–32.

³⁰⁹ Abul Fazl, *The Akbarnama of Abu'l Fazl. Vol. I*, trans. Henry Beveridge (Calcutta: Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1897), 37; Asher, *Architecture of Mughal India*, 40; Malecka, "Solar Symbolism of the Mughal Thrones", 24–32; Asher, "A Ray from the Sun," 170.

³¹⁰ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 6.

Elephants were also utilised to express the emperor's power and authority through administration of the king's justice, serving as imperial executioners.³¹¹ We find the earliest recorded instance of this among the Mughals with Babur who issued this punishment to one of his cooks who tried to poison him.³¹² Using elephants to trample enemies of the state came to be actively used as imperial punishment by his successors in the years to come. Consequently, anyone found guilty of mistreating or causing harm to an elephant across the land could be sentenced to death or sold as a slave.³¹³

Taken together, this shift in accepting the elephant as the symbol of imperial power and sovereignty also implied that Akbar was embracing a part of the indigenous cultural symbolisms of the Indian subcontinent over antecedents from Central Asia, where his ancestors were originally from.³¹⁴ Owing to this, the elephant tended to be a steady presence in both Mughal art and architecture as well, generally portrayed to appear in close proximity to the emperor or the spaces that represented his authority. This is particularly evident in the case of paintings of the Mughal emperor holding court where the elephant, if included, is placed either in the audience or as sculptures immediately below the emperor's *jharokha* (balcony), upon which the attendants stood. However, the elephant was not restricted just to art. The elephant became a part of the Mughal architectural scheme too where they appeared as a decorative motif in many settings, from column capitals to even life-size sculptures made of black marble which flanked the Delhi Gate of the Red Fort in Delhi (Fig. 3). A cursory understanding of this close relationship of the emperor and the elephant opens the way to explore the case of the Mughal processions under consideration.

³¹¹ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 11.

³¹² Babur, *The Baburnama: Memoirs of Babur, Prince and Emperor*, trans. Wheeler M Thackston (New York: Modern Library, 2002), 368.

³¹³ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 12.

³¹⁴ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 92–114.

Figure 1: Portrait of the imperial elephant called 'Alam Guman Gajraj' which was presented to the Mughal Emperor Jahangir in 1614. Artist: Bichitr, 1640. Source: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Public Domain.

Figure 2: Shah Jahan watching an elephant fight from the jharokha window (possibly at Agra Fort). Folio from Padshahnama. Artist: Bulaqi, 1639. Source: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Public Domain.

4. Elephants in Mughal Processions

This section explores the two broad types of processions that are considered in this study, which are thematically divided based on the distance that was covered and the nature of the procession. For the first category, the imperial march, the focus will be on the role of the elephant in the procession where the Mughal emperor shifts his residence from one city to another, whereas the second category will examine the festive procession, particularly the Friday procession to the Jama Masjid in Shahjahanabad (Old Delhi).

4.1. The Imperial March

In its initial decades, empire building was a laborious task which demanded constant movement of the emperor within his domains. The requirement for this movement could arise due to a plethora of reasons ranging from military campaigns, civil war, quelling rebellions and pilgrimage to Sufi shrines or just seeking a temporary respite from the harsh Indian summers. However, the resulting march meant that both the court as well as the household would be accompanying the emperor as a procession.³¹⁵ The elephant came to play an important role in this type of procession as it served as the mount that carried not only the emperor, but his core entourage, including the accompanying family (generally covered from public view), courtiers, as well as carrying the bulk of the baggage.³¹⁶ Travel accounts of this procession type are available from the time of two emperors, Shah Jahan (r. 1628-1658) and Aurangzeb (r. 1658-1707), both being eye-witness accounts by Europeans. Shah Jahan's procession from Agra to Lahore (approximately 600 km) was recorded by an anonymous Italian who observed the start of the procession, giving us the public's perspective to the spectacle, while Aurangzeb's procession was documented by François Bernier, a French physician and traveller who served the emperor and was thus a part of the procession.³¹⁷

³¹⁵ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 13.

³¹⁶ Buckingham, "Symbolism and Power," 13.

³¹⁷ Aniruddha Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document on the March of Shah Jahan from Agra to Lahore in September 1638," *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* 56 (1995): 220–26, 220; François Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire, A.D. 1656-1668*, ed. Vincent A Smith, trans. Archibald Constable (London: Oxford University Press, 1934), 280.

At the outset, both these processions, which took place within a span of fifty years from each other, had significant overlaps. The similarity in the details of the processions in both travel accounts point to the fact that general rules were codified for this type of a march.³¹⁸ With its official commencement set for a time deemed as auspicious by astrologers, these processions tended to be exceptionally large in scale, with estimates in the accounts putting the total number of participants at 125,000, where the soldiers alone accounted for 40,000.³¹⁹ The general structure of this procession was composed of three broad sections, where the first section comprised workers and the emperor's guards, which was subsequently followed by the emperor, his family and important nobles, all of whom rode on elephants, while the third section was made up of women from the extended family of the emperor, women of the harem, servants and eunuchs, among others.³²⁰ The massive scale of the procession involved an equally massive entourage of elephants, horses, camels and oxen that carried people, provisions, water and baggage.³²¹

Although this procession was not one primarily aimed at exhibiting pomp and prestige of the emperor, the opportunity was not missed since this long procession clearly made for a spectacle throughout the lands through which it passed. The large army that accompanied the procession made for a display of strength while the unending train of elephants and other animals made for a spectacle which represented the sovereign and his power. This ultimately played out as a way to claim power and legitimacy in regions on the fringes of imperial power centres which were otherwise not accustomed to such grand imperial displays. Chaplain Edward Terry, who was part of the British delegation of Sir Thomas Roe (1615-1619) to the Mughal court of Jahangir, called the procession 'a walking common-wealth' and calculated that it would take twelve hours for the entire procession to pass one particular point.³²² Meanwhile, Sir Thomas Roe had posited that when the procession stopped to rest for the night, it would take an area of twenty miles in circumference, essentially resembling a small town with regular streets.³²³ The location allotted for all participants inside the camp remained identical each time they camped,

³¹⁸ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 222.

³¹⁹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220, 222.

³²⁰ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²¹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²² Edward Terry, *A Voyage to East-India* (London: W. Cater, 1777), 399-400; Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²³ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

so that it was easier for the people in the procession to find their way.³²⁴ To fasten the process, the emperor and the nobles used additional tents that were set up at the next camping point in advance of the procession's arrival.³²⁵ Additionally, since the elephants carried their riders at an elevated height, imperial subjects were not allowed to watch the procession from upper floors or terraces of buildings.³²⁶ The routes were also cleared in advance and the road was dusted and provided with palisades on sides to prevent crowds from coming close.³²⁷

The elephants were also tasked with carrying the dynastic insignia, where each of the six symbols of the insignia were carried on separate elephants. The symbols of the insignia included two gold fish suspended on the sides of a bow, the face of a sun with rays, the golden hand of Fatima, the head of a horse, the head of a lion-like beast and lastly an imperial umbrella.³²⁸ Raising these golden insignia on richly decorated gilt staffs from a richly caparisoned elephant ensured that the insignia would remain at one of the highest points of elevation for the entire length of the procession, making it one of the most visible elements as well in the longest distance.³²⁹

A strict hierarchy was observed throughout the procession prior to its commencement itself. The aforementioned anonymous Italian noted that the emperor determined the extent of followers that were to accompany him as well as his nobles, in addition to paying in advance for the bazaar that accompanied the procession to procure goods required in advance.³³⁰ Bernier cited that the emperor used six hundred elephants just for himself, with the biggest and highest ranked elephants being the ones he and his family rode on, while a thousand camels were used to carry the baggage and the kitchen of the emperor.³³¹ The nobles followed suit and employed their own elephants, camels and horses for themselves according to their rank.³³² The general hierarchy implied that the nobles who travelled closer to the emperor had a higher rank, suggesting that the emperor was the centre of the procession and he was always portrayed on his

³²⁴ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²⁵ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 154.

³²⁶ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²⁷ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 220.

³²⁸ William Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal: The Fall of a Dynasty, Delhi 1857* (London: Bloomsbury, 2006), Chapter 1. Dalrymple describes the procession of the last Mughal ruler, Bahadur Shah Zafar, in detail in this chapter.

³²⁹ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³³⁰ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 222.

³³¹ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³² Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

elephant for this type of procession.³³³ Thus, the number of elephants that each person in this procession owned could reveal their status and rank at court while their distance from the centre of the procession, i.e. from the emperor, determined their standing in the system.³³⁴

This type of procession largely disappeared after the reign of Aurangzeb as the empire began its rapid decline to the point where the Mughal Emperor started to be confined to the capital city of Shahjahanabad (Old Delhi). However, the Friday procession, which will be analysed next, continued until the very end of the dynasty. Despite the decline of the empire, the elephant still retained its symbolic meanings of kingship even when the British steadily took over administration of large swathes of India over the years. While the subsequent introduction of railways in the subcontinent by the British ended the need for the elephant to serve logistical needs to a large extent, the elephant's role in imperial processions continued well into twentieth century colonial India.

4.2. The Friday Procession

In stark contrast to the imperial march, the Friday procession was one of the shortest imperial processions in terms of distance covered while simultaneously being one of the most common in terms of frequency. The elephant played a central role in this short procession of the Mughal Emperor from his palace to the congregational mosque in his capital city on Fridays. In order to study this procession, this section will focus on this procession type in Delhi.

The walled city of Shahjahanabad was built by Shah Jahan in 1639 and became the capital of the Mughal Empire, replacing Agra which had remained one of the capitals during the reigns of his predecessors.³³⁵ One of the reasons given for this change of capital by Shah Jahan's court historian, Muhammad Salih Kanbo, was that the streets of Agra were too narrow, winding and crowded and as such were a hindrance for the proper conduct of royal processions.³³⁶ This concern was rectified in the planning of Shahjahanabad which utilised two primary ceremonial

³³³ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³⁴ Ray, "An Anonymous Contemporary Italian Document," 223.

³³⁵ Percival Spear, *The Delhi Omnibus*, ed. Robert Eric Frykenberg (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2008), 26.

³³⁶ Muhammad Salih Kanbo, *Amal-i-Šālih; or, Shāh Jahān Nāmāh, of Muḥammad Sālih Kaṃbō*, Vol. III, trans. Ghulam Yazdani (Calcutta: Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1927), 26-27.

axes to connect the Red Fort (the emperor's residence) to the two prominent gates at the outer walls of the city. Although the congregational mosque, the Jama Masjid (one of the largest mosques in India), was built by Shah Jahan in 1656 alongside the construction of the city, it was not directly placed in these two major ceremonial axes. Instead, it occupied a position between the two axes while still in close proximity to the Red Fort (within a kilometre). There was a direct ceremonial street leading to the East entrance of the Jama Masjid from the Delhi Gate of the Red Fort, which was used by the Mughal emperors for their Friday processions. The Delhi Gate of the Red Fort was also coincidentally flanked by life-size models of elephants made of marble, which still stand today (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: George V, King of England, passing through the Delhi Gate at the Red Fort in Delhi, 1911. Two life-size models of elephants made of marble can be seen in the background. Source gallica.bnf.fr / Bibliothèque nationale de France. Public Domain.

The most detailed description of the Friday procession from Shah Jahan's time was given by François Bernier. According to Bernier, prior to the Friday procession from the Red Fort to the Jama Masjid, the streets on the procession route were watered to settle the dust and reduce the heat.³³⁷ Following this, three hundred musketeers marched out and formed an avenue by lining up on both sides of the wide street up to the Jama Masjid.³³⁸ The procession proper began with up to six horsemen riding out in front to clear the path for the emperor, who subsequently rode out on top of a richly caparisoned elephant, seated under a canopy supported by gilt pillars.³³⁹ The elephant maintained a considerable distance behind the horsemen so that the dust that would be kicked up by the horses would not affect the emperor.³⁴⁰ The emperor was closely followed in procession by high-ranking members of the nobility on horseback or palanquins, along with mace bearers.³⁴¹ Bernier considered this procession to not match up to grand processions he had witnessed in Europe but nevertheless accepted it to possess a magnificence of a different character.³⁴² Therefore, it is worth noting that only the emperor used the elephant on this occasion, whereby he occupied the highest point in the procession while also occupying the middle position yet again in the arrangement, similar to the imperial march but in a much smaller scale.

In addition to the Friday processions, elephants were the imperial mount of both the emperor as well as his family on other festive occasions that involved a processional element, such as imperial wedding processions or the Eid procession, among others, which continued with all pomp and regalia even until the very end of the dynasty in the 1850s. While space constraints restrict a detailed dive into these other avenues that involved processions, what is essential to note is that despite the changes in geopolitical realities for the Mughal dynasty, brought about by its decline starting in the eighteenth century, the richly caparisoned elephant still served as the symbol of kingship through which the emperor was presented to the public during an imperial procession. Essentially, the elephant in procession functioned as a visible reminder of the

³³⁷ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³³⁸ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³³⁹ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴⁰ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴¹ Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

³⁴² Bernier, *Travels in the Mogul Empire*, 280.

continuities from the heyday of the empire, even as the Mughal monarch held very little power towards the end.

5. Changing Times

The Mughal dynasty officially came to an end in India following the uprising of 1857 against the English East India Company rule.³⁴³ Bahadur Shah Zafar, the last Mughal monarch, was exiled to Rangoon (Myanmar) along with his family while the control of British India passed from the English East India Company to the British Crown.³⁴⁴ The ensuing British colonial rule led to many large scale displays of pomp and power by the British, where the elephant found itself being incorporated into these new imperial frameworks at a time of great technological advancements. The legacy of the historic association of the Indian elephant with sovereignty and power in the Indian subcontinent and all its symbolisms associated with royalty were integrated and fully utilised by these new rulers of India in legitimising and proclaiming their rule. Some of the best examples to witness this play out was in the case of the Delhi Durbar processions.

Delhi Durbars were grand coronation ceremonies held in India for the British monarch in order to bestow them with the rank of ‘Emperor/Empress of India’.³⁴⁵ Out of the three Delhi Durbars, held for Queen Victoria (1877), Edward VII (1903) and George V (1911), the elephant was featured as a prominent part of the pompous and enormous processions that took place, particularly in the 1903 Delhi Durbar (Fig. 4).³⁴⁶ The elephants shined in full regalia while carrying the representatives of the highest offices of British power as well as Indian kings in procession. It is worth noting that the British selected the elephant as the platform to display themselves from during these processions despite it taking place in an era with access to motorised vehicles. Although this could have been taken as an opportunity to convey technological superiority over their colony, it did not happen in that manner. Instead, it can be argued that the elephant was opted precisely due to its symbolism related to kingship and

³⁴³ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³⁴⁴ Dalrymple, *The Last Mughal*, Chapter 1.

³⁴⁵ Julie F. Codell, ed., *Power and Resistance: The Delhi Coronation Durbars* (Ahmedabad: Mapin Publishing Pvt. Ltd and The Alkazi Collection of Photography, 2012); Julie F Codell, “On the Delhi Coronation Durbars, 1877, 1903, 1911,” *BRANCH*, June 2012, https://branchcollective.org/?ps_articles=julie-codell-on-the-delhi-coronation-durbars-1877-1903-1911.

³⁴⁶ Codell, *Power and Resistance*; Codell, “On the Delhi Coronation Durbars, 1877, 1903, 1911.”

legitimacy. However, the Delhi Durbar of 1911 presented a unique moment to further explore how deeply the concept of kingship was intertwined with the elephant in the Indian cultural imagination. When the British monarch, George V, joined the imperial procession as part of the durbar festivities (Fig. 3), his reluctance to ride the elephant, choosing instead to ride a horse, was reported to have caused considerable confusion among the Indian onlookers, for a monarch was traditionally expected to ride the elephant in a procession, ultimately causing the king and his exalted status to be less effectively conveyed in this context when he appeared on horseback.³⁴⁷ Thus, the legacy of the elephant in these processions, which existed long before the Mughals came to India, continued long after them, demonstrating the persistence of the image of the elephant and its close association with kingship in the Indian psyche.

Figure 4: Photograph of the British Viceroy’s caparisoned elephant kneeling down, likely as part of the Delhi Durbar of 1877. Photographers: Bourne & Shepherd, 1877. Source: The J. Paul Getty Museum, Los Angeles. Public Domain.

³⁴⁷ Charles W. Nuckolls, “The Durbar Incident,” *Modern Asian Studies* 24, no. 3 (1990): 529–59, 535; Stephen Bottomore, “‘Have You Seen the Gaekwar Bob?’: Filming the 1911 De i Durba” *Historical Journal of Film, Radio and Television* 17, no. 3 (1997)

5. Conclusion

With a deeper understanding of Mughal processions that were analysed in this paper, this study demonstrated the common roles that elephants tended to serve in imperial processions. For this, the paper explored two broad types of processions that were thematically divided based on two aspects, the distance that was covered and the nature of the procession, specifically the imperial march and the Friday procession. Through examining these processions, it was noted that the elephant played a key role as the imperial mount of the emperor and his family and other important members from the court and nobility. Regardless of the type of procession, the emperor always rode on the biggest elephant from the imperial stables which held him at the highest elevated position in the procession and thus exalted his power and prestige. Additionally, the emperor tended to occupy a position close to the middle of the procession in both these cases. The second notable feature pertained to dynastic and imperial insignia, which were also displayed atop the elephant during procession, particularly in the imperial march. In addition to its role in processions, the Mughals also actively employed the elephant for other avenues of their life where the elephant remained a royal prerogative, which included royal hunts, royal entertainment, dispensation of justice etc. Through focusing on the processional element of the elephant, the study also highlighted the syncretic underpinnings behind how the Mughals, particularly during Akbar's rule, expertly adopted a tradition inherent to India to fit the needs of their growing empire. As such, this case study stands to demonstrate a unique instance where an incoming dynasty from Central Asia came to find an exceptional way to combine their background with the varied cultures that they came across while ruling over India.

The legacy of the elephant endured long after the Mughal dynasty ended, since its associations to power and legitimacy came to be absorbed and adopted by the British as they became the new rulers of India. Even in the age of motorised vehicles, using elephants in the pompous Delhi Durbar processions gave the British the symbolic gesture of wielding power over their colonial possessions in India. Today, the elephant continues to hold considerable cultural value in many parts of India where they are an integral part of processions. However, its association with Indian kingship have followed the path of the kingdoms in the subcontinent itself as they joined the newly independent states of India or Pakistan following independence

from British rule in 1947. Most of the elephant habitats mentioned in the Mughal texts do not sustain elephant populations today and though elephants have survived well into our time, unlike other species that went extinct in India after the Mughal period (Asiatic cheetah for instance), the elephant is an animal fighting for survival today as its habitats lessen and its conflicts with humans increase. Nevertheless, the elephant remains as an enduring symbol of an inherently Indian concept of kingship that has its roots since the earliest history in the region, which came to be widely adopted by both the societies that inhabited it as well as by foreign dynasties that settled to rule, of which, the Mughal case was analysed in this paper through their processions.

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